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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Dissemination and Communication Plan specifies the dissemination strategy, activities, and materials that SMART-electron intends to use over the lifetime of the Project, with the goal of making it as visible as possible and of disseminating the Project's results as widely as possible.

The dissemination and engagement activities are targeted to reach:

- the scientific research community, including national research agencies
- science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science
- audiences from projects similar to SMART-electron
- high-school students
- policy-group members
- private-enterprise scientists and managers.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan identifies the methods to be employed to reach each of these target groups, how to tune the messages accordingly, and the expected outcome of those activities.

Central to the identity and presence of SMART-electron is the Project Website, whose role is described in this document and whose design is discussed in more detail in *D6.1 Project logo and webpage*.

In addition, the current document describes how SMART-electron intends to capitalise on the potential of social media (SM) for informing and spreading awareness on the project, as well as engaging with a wider audience.

Finally, Conferences and Edit-A-Thons will also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process, and, together with the Website and SM profiles, will ensure that the results will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

This document serves as an easy-to-use internal guide for the project partners. In addition, it describes the dissemination methodologies and activities to be carried out by partners in the project and how these processes will be monitored.

A further aim of this document is to streamline and standardise the procedures concerning the project's dissemination activities and to provide SMART-electron partners with branding guidelines to be adopted. The standardisation of procedures will also help the project management in monitoring and reporting activities and outcomes.

We acknowledge that the present document is built on the successful dissemination experiences and strategies of previous European projects such as EAGLE, [Q-SORT](#) and [MINEON](#).

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document features 6 chapters.

Chapter 1, the Introduction, provides a brief overview of the deliverable's objectives.

Chapter 2 describes the goals that SMART-electron intends to reach through its dissemination, communication and engagement activities as described in the DoA.

Chapter 3 describes the target audience to be reached. SMART-electron addresses the research community, the general public, the contributing community (i.e. academia, private sector), government and policy bodies.

Chapter 4 analyses the variety of dissemination, communication, and engagement methods to be adopted with the goal of making the Project, its outcomes, and its results known.

Chapter 5 describes how the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities will be continuously evaluated and according to which criteria.

Chapter 6 briefly summarises the conclusions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Within the SMART-electron project the dissemination and communication plan concerns:

- All partners
- All WP leaders
- Coordination/admin staff
- Web site managers

with a particular emphasis on the staff that is responsible for each institution's communication activities.

In addition, since this is a public document and is available on the Project Website, the plan will be accessible by external parties interested in the dissemination plan of the SMART-electron project.

This deliverable aims to function as an easy-to-use internal guide for the SMART-electron network.

It describes all the elements required for the effective execution of the SMART-electron Dissemination and communication, i.e.:

1. the objectives the project intends to reach through its dissemination activities;
2. the target audiences, describing their interests and characteristics;
3. the methods and the timetable of the results' dissemination to the target audiences;
4. the branding/graphic design guidelines.

This deliverable has been updated in accordance with the project's evolving needs, activities, and achievements.

2 WHY AND WHAT - GOALS

The aim of SMART-electron's outreach is to spread awareness of concepts, worldviews, and notions generated by the science behind the project. It will do so by broadcasting exciting, meaningful 'information nuggets' online through a variety of strategies, as well as by involving citizens in participatory events (and/or their online version) pertaining to the world of science and science culture. In this effort, SMART-electron will also take advantage of the combined experience and capacity of its Consortium members.

SMART-electron aims to achieve the following objectives through its dissemination, communication and public engagement activities:

1. To spread knowledge of the Project internationally amongst non-specialists through communication and engagement activities. This has the twin goals of spreading knowledge and awareness about science, as well as about EU-funded world-class research.
2. To spread knowledge of the Project amongst other scientists through dissemination, so as to foster future uptake of resulting SMART-electron-related techniques and technologies.
3. To promote science vocation among young people through communication and engagement.
4. To foster through dissemination the enlargement of SMART-electron's scientific network, for further future collaborations.

5. To seek to meaningfully inform relevant policy-group members and decision makers in public institutions devoted to science funding.
6. To make European enterprises aware of the opportunities afforded by EC R&I projects.

Through this Dissemination and Communication Plan, WP6 intends to facilitate the achievement of the above-mentioned goals, including all the while the contributions of all SMART-electron partners and WP Leaders.

SMART-electron overall dissemination, communication and engagement ethos emphasises inclusiveness. This results in a fundamentally grassroots approach to science communication and in the involvement of civil society organisations such as the Wikimedia Foundation. The overall aim is to reverse the usually adopted strategies by embracing an inductive rather than a deductive approach to the communication of science. Therefore, the focus tends to be, rather than on 'science made understandable to people', on 'people made to participate in science initiatives'. Gender issues in science will be treated with particular attention.

All dissemination and communication activities will be conducted under the coordination of the partner QED, which will ensure the delivery of a consistent message from the Project to the 'outer world'.

3 WHO – THE SMART-ELECTRON TARGET AUDIENCE

The various target groups for SMART-electron were determined based on the overall goals of dissemination and engagement. In decreasing order of importance, and of overall expected reach, they are: the research community, science enthusiasts and the curious, audiences from SMART-electron 'sister' projects, high-school students, policy-group members, private-enterprise scientists and managers, and also the general public. Within each of these demographics, special consideration will be given -within the constraints of SMART-electron's limited funding for outreach- to the so-called 'silent stakeholders', i.e. disadvantaged or minority categories such as women, the elderly, the poor.

The above target audiences are made up of either specialists (i.e. scientists) or non-specialists. Reaching specialists is important for the uptake of the science and technology developed in SMART-electron. Reaching non-specialists is important as a cultural mission in general, but also to spread awareness about cutting-edge research, its importance, and how adequately the EU is funding it.

3.1 The research community

This community is represented by researchers and experts working in the fields of nanoscience, electron microscopy, quantum optics, and solid-state physics, biochemistry, biology in general - but also less immediately-related disciplines such as accelerator physics and quantum computing. All these scientists can potentially benefit from the results of the project, either from the application of the project in their respective disciplines or from the adoption of techniques/tools developed for SMART-electron. We also consider national groups, European and international organisations (such as the European Microscopy Society) to be part of this community.

3.1.1 National research-agency scientists

A significant subset of the research community, this large and diverse group can be easily reached through specialised channels (e.g. mailing lists) and may benefit from SMART-electron scientific results by reusing them at a national level - e.g. by adopting SE-related technologies, theory, and practices. Considering that several partners are also involved in European projects dealing with e-infrastructures, the transparent sharing of information relating to SMART-electron open data serves to inform these groups as well as

e-infrastructure providers and managers. Also, open data made available by SMART-electron might possibly find use as training datasets for the machine learning community.

3.2 Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science

Citizens who have an interest in science, from different countries and from a wide demographics, are our prime non-specialist target, as they are easier to reach -thanks to already-existing communities and groups of interest- and much more likely to appreciate SMART-electron's scientific and aesthetic aspects. It is important to reach this large group both as a cultural mission as well as to inform taxpayers on how public moneys are being invested.

Besides a variety of online posts and initiatives (see Section 4), events targeted to reach this demographic, such as the SMART-electron Science Bash events, will take place in new, unusual locations generally not taken into consideration for the public understanding of science; these might be pubs (possibly as Pint of Science events), clubs, cafès; but also music and art festivals happening in the same city. The choice of these new locations aims to extend the reach of SMART-electron to those who are interested in science but generally don't frequent traditional venues. This also reflects our overall preoccupation with trying to reach the so-called 'silent stakeholders', i.e. under-represented portions of the public such as women, the elderly, the poorer, recent immigrants. Content-wise, references to local/regional conditions will be featured whenever possible, leveraging SMART-electron partners' existing connections to local territories. Unfortunately, SMART-electron's limited budget allows just for a handful of live events, but these will be highly targeted and their success will serve as a metrics for future such like initiatives in EC projects. Regular mini-events for this demographic will also comprise Wikimedia Edit-a-thons.

3.3 Audiences from SMART-electron 'sister' projects

SMART-electron shares similar target audiences with other quantum technology and electron microscopy projects. Also, other FET projects share similar non-specialist target audiences with SMART-electron.

Outreach synergies with these projects hold the potential for a multiplier effect. Collaboration with sister projects is also important in order to optimise effort and avoid duplication of messages. The projects that could benefit from dissemination/engagement synergies with SMART-electron are listed in Section 4.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels.

3.4 High-school students

This demographics is important in general because it represents the citizens of tomorrow. It is also strategically important to reach in order to begin to address the vocational crisis in science subjects that is being felt in some EU countries. The low proportion of students and graduates in science and technology is, in fact, a concern for future innovation capacity in the EU. Putting high-school students in touch with the beauty and the challenges of cutting-edge research in science is one of SMART-electron aims. Providing informal science education by illustrating key concepts related to SMART-electron is another. Since high-school students are highly active on social networks, these will be our primary conduit.

3.5 Policy-group members

This target group includes policy makers at the national and European levels.

At the European Level the target is mainly represented by the Member States and by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission which defines and implements European Research and Innovation (R&I) policy with a view to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy and its key flagship initiative, the Innovation Union. Communication with this group is important in order to spread awareness of recent scientific developments as well as to propose best practices and improvements in how resources for R&I are invested.

Dissemination targeted to these users is crucial for the sustainability of the Project. Disseminating SMART-electron results among government ministries and agencies, which control or lobby for funding research institutions of all sorts, is valuable in order for the SMART-electron partners to be supported in the future at the national government level. Communication towards this group is fundamental to ensure a more adequate level of national funding for fundamental research, which, with a few exceptions, is not funded by the EU. This is of paramount importance in order to keep alive the research ecosystem.

3.6 Private-enterprise scientists and managers

It is important to target this group so that interested parties become aware of the opportunities provided by the FET programme for the private sector. Two enterprises, FEI/Thermo Fisher (a technology company) and QED (a media production company) are already part of the SMART-electron consortium and can provide insights.

3.7 Notes on the general public

The focus of SMART-electron dissemination and engagement is to increase awareness among selected stakeholders, so as to maximise the return on the investment made on these activities. However, insofar as possible given the limited resources allotted to WP6, we want to also try to address the wider public. Whilst it is generally considered futile to try to address a generalist audience without massive communication resources, we will nevertheless be taking a number of steps so as to ensure that our activities do not alienate a mass audience. Therefore, as a general principle, we will:

- employ friendly, inclusive, and non intimidating language
- seek to post high-quality, fresh content with far-reaching appeal
- include hashtags and channels that might help us reach new audiences
- strive to hold engagement events in new, non-intimidating locations such as pubs and cafès.

The latter will allow SMART-electron to reach new audiences that tend to avoid the more traditional spaces that are generally being used to communicate science.

3.8 General overview of target groups and corresponding messages

The following table summarises the type of audience, the messages to be communicated, the foreseen impact, and the partners' involvement.

AUDIENCE	MESSAGE TO BE COMMUNICATED ¹	MAIN IMPACT	SMART-electron ACTORS INVOLVED
The research community	New SE-related tools, techniques, theory are available or are being developed with	National, European, International	All partners, WP Leaders and EAB

¹ Hashtags are used here for the sake of conciseness

	<p>potential applications <i>in your domain</i></p> <p>#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch</p> <p>[other more specific hashtags will also be used]</p>		
National research-agency scientists	<p>New SE-related tools, techniques, theory are available or are being developed with potential applications <i>in your domain</i></p> <p>#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch</p> <p>[other more specific hashtags will also be used]</p>	National, European, International	All partners
Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science	<p>Science is beautiful Research is important The EU invests in research</p> <p>#ScienceIsCool #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #FundResearchForAbetterWorld</p>	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED
Audiences from SMART-electron 'sister' projects	<p>#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #ScienceIsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow</p>	National, European, International	All partners, but mainly WP leaders
High school students	<p>#ScienceIsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow</p>	National, European	All partners
Policy groups, agencies and governments	<p>Make more regular funding available for fundamental research at the national level Ask for increased R&I budget at EU level</p> <p>#MakingTheFutureHappenNow #MoreWomenGirlsInSTEM #FundResearchForAbetterWorld #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch</p>	National, European, International	All partners

Private-enterprise scientists and managers	EU funding is available for enterprises that want to do research #EUhelpsEnterprises #EUfundsResearch #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European	All partners
General Public	#ScienceIsCool #EUfundsResearch #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED

3.9 Cross-cutting target groups: common tags and hashtags

Some hashtags and tags cut across all the above demographics. These are chosen in order to reach out to established audiences pertaining to other existing social media entities or to new or existing audiences clustering around certain topics. Our rule of thumb for tagging is to include

- all SMART-electron partners and partners of each specific initiative;
- the entities in their extended network;
- any active channels from the EU on the chosen medium/media;
- personal profiles in the case of involved or influential individuals.

These common tags and hashtags are based on either main brand / concept fostering, e.g.:
#SMART-electron #EUfunded #FET #pintofscience #sciencebash #EUE

Or on shared institutions / sister projects / brands, e.g.:

@EU_Commission @Wikimedia @FET_EU @EU_H2020 @ERC_Research @FETX @CERN
@OpenAIRE_eu @iew2019 #EICFTW @EUScienceInnov @StampaCnr @MPI_Light @UofGOS
@EIC @EIC_EU @fet_eu @FETFX_EU #CNRNANO #emiliaromagnaopen @FetBriefing
@RegioneER @PorFesrER @Thermofisher @thermosciEMSpec @Wikimedialitalia
@WikimediaDE @HorizonMagEU #FutureTechWeek

Or on shared themes, e.g.:

#STEM #openlabs #education
#science #technology, #innovation
#Microscopy #TEM #electronmicroscopy #nanotechnology #nanoscience #hologram
#womeninscience @WomenScienceDay @WomenInOptics @4womeninscience
#sciencewelike #sciencecomm #scicomm
#sneakpreview
#nails #design #beautytips #beauty
#totebag #autumn

Or on relevant scientists' / politicians' / SMM profiles.

This type of tagging is especially useful for LinkedIn posts, in order to reach scientists or science managers who might be interested in SMART-electron research or technologies.

Or on relevant groups of interest, e.g.:

EU Science & Innovation, Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Group, Cryo Microscopy Group, Europe's Digital Agenda Initiatives, Microscopy, Nanotechnology World Network, Accelerating Microscopy, Research and Executive Agency, European Innovation Council.

On Twitter, popular or trending hashtags related to the intended post at the moment of posting are also employed. These include hashtags pertaining to specific newsworthy events and hashtags on relevant themes.

4 How - METHODOLOGY

The SMART-electron project makes use of a variety of dissemination and public engagement methods.

As a general remark, given the limited budget that EC projects are able to allot to Dissemination efforts, promotion of SMART-electron through traditional mass media is not economically viable, in the sense that advertising is too expensive for adequately promoting SMART-electron. On the other hand, online communication, especially through social media, is much cheaper and can be tailored with great precision to very specific groups - defined by specific interests, age range, geographic location. It therefore provides a truly optimal return on investment, which is why it is used extensively for SMART-electron.

Messages vary through the lifetime of the Project. In the initial phases, dissemination is more focused on encouraging awareness of the project, while during the last year the Project will focus on promoting its major achievements.

SMART-electron aims to expand the capacity of European and national science actors to effect better societal engagement. SMART-electron aims to support a shift towards a more dynamic relationship between science and society. The project aims to achieve this objective by using and exploring recent cutting-edge innovation practices in public engagement (see Events in Section 4.3) within this composite and multifaceted field.

Inclusive, participatory events such as the Wiki Edit-a-thon, as well as the special attention paid to gender issues and minority stakeholders, also make SMART-electron RRI-compliant. SMART-electron fully shares the RRI aim of engaging society in open science and innovation.

Finally, compliance with Open Science and Open Innovation EC policies is ensured by the project-specific Open Data Management Plan.

The following paragraphs briefly summarise our approach.

4.1 SMART-electron Branding Guidelines

When we say the ‘branding guidelines’ of the project, we mean a set of elements and guidelines that should characterise the institutional communication of the project in order to simplify and make recognisable our communication activities (project visual identity, in short, see also *D6.1 Project logo and webpage*).

Given the particular nature of the SMART-electron content, we feel it is important to pay attention to our communications to both specialised audiences and external, non-specialised audiences. In particular, the development of the following elements has been considered for SMART-electron's branding efforts:

1. Basic elements (see also: *D6.1 Project logo and webpage*)

- Brand Logo

SMART-electron logo- Red Fluo version

- Branding architecture, meaning a cohesive system of typographical rules, visual relations and hierarchies between the brand-logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to it (e.g. the SMART-electron brand-logotype and event titles)

2. Web (see also: *D6.1 Project logo and webpage*)

Templates for the web pages (that are compatible with the CMS of the portal), in particular:

- main portal page;
- general page template;
- events pages template; news template, partners' page template;
- contacts page template / Who We Are, etc.

The SMART-electron website is conceived for both desktop and mobile use

SMART-electron home page

3. Printed materials

- Three-sided A4 foldable Project brochure design;
- SMART-electron branded tote bag design;
- 4x A2 Project Conference poster designs;

- 1x Project vinyl banner design;
- 4x SMART-electron conferences' Book of Abstracts designs;
- A4 SMART-electron folder design.

These assets will be printed in the quantities that QED deems sufficient for the achievement of the dissemination and communication goals.

Mock-ups of possible future designs based on the SMART-electron logo

4. Ready-to-use layouts

- PowerPoint/Keynote template for presentations;
- A4 template for SMART-electron-headed paper for invitations and courteous communications
- Electronic communication documents (e.g. outreach toolkits).

4.2 Adjusting the language according to the target audience

The SMART-electron project aims to develop knowledge and tools that can be technically complex and challenging. The language we use in order to communicate these ideas is therefore critical. Its importance cannot be underestimated, for it can make the difference between accepting or dismissing important concepts.

Therefore, the same messages, when targeted at different audiences, often need to be expressed in different ways: the language used must become more or less technical according to the intended audience it is addressing. For example, writing a paper for a scientific journal demands a more technical language, facilitating the reading with images, schemas, and tables. On the other hand, a short paper for the institution's newsletter or website needs to be expressed in non-technical terms using language that the audience is familiar with. Writing for the Web in general needs to present ideas clearly, and concisely. Also, crucially, there is a need to communicate complex concepts to other scientists from different fields (e.g. communicating physics to biologists). This is an intermediate, interdisciplinary level of communication.

Therefore, SMART-electron can be said to have, in general, at least three distinct levels of communication: highly specialistic, interdisciplinary, and general public.

Specialistic communication is taken care of by the peer-reviewed articles that the Project begets, whose manuscripts are also Project Deliverables.

On the other hand, dedicated Wikipedia articles (see 4.3 below) were conceived as tools for the communication of information at all three different levels. Wikipedia articles can function as an interactive online lexicon that is particularly flexible and user-friendly, and which moreover is available to anyone. This is why we decided to invest time and resources in the **Wiki Edit-a-thons**.

4.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels

In this section we summarise the main conduits through which the Project will reach its intended target groups.

- **SMART-electron Project Website**

The SMART-electron website has already been described in *D6.1 project logo and webpage*, which illustrates its aims, the users that it targets, the adopted CMS, the structure of the public and reserved areas, the implementation work, services, editorial board, and the tools for monitoring.

The SMART-electron website is the centre of the dissemination and communication strategy of SMART-electron. It facilitates the management of the **community** created around the project activities. The members of the community will be strongly encouraged to participate, as most of the communication will occur online.

The Website presents the project to all target audiences and gives detailed, tailored information to stakeholders and journalists on project progress, activities, and results (among other things). The aim is to publish news, data, and other relevant project deliverables in a way that can be useful to other researchers and potential business partners.

The website also features:

- a dedicated **News section** for the public at large, in which project activities are presented in a non-technical way; this section also includes photos and may include short mobile videos taken by project scientists, documenting what is going on;
- attached social media groups (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Twitter);
- a **Reserved Area** – which only partners can access – for the exchange of working documents
- Web pages devoted to **layperson's explanations and introductions to basic physics concepts** at the heart of the project;
- a Web page devoted to the **scientific publications** produced by SMART-electron.

SMART-electron - News page

Users visiting the Website are thus able to:

- ★ browse Project News
 - ★ download public files such as the latest Press Release and Outreach Toolkit, as well as published articles and public deliverables
 - ★ replay the Interdisciplinary Webinars
 - ★ access further reading about the science behind the project (Meet Your Scientist, links to online resources, etc.)
 - ★ contact SMART-electron scientists to ask questions
 - ★ browse SMART-electron past and upcoming Events
 - ★ browse beautiful TEM images
 - ★ upload and download work files in the password-protected Reserved Area
- **Partners' websites**

Partners are encouraged to disseminate SMART-electron activities and outcomes on their own institutional websites, periodically updating news, and links to relevant documentation. Partners have been asked to put links to the SMART-electron Website on their institutional websites, so as to increase its Google PageRank.
 - **Social networks**

Dedicated social network profiles are a fundamental part of the Project's identity. In fact, a lively SN presence allows us to gradually build a community of interested users around SMART-electron. This is the most effective way to ensure visibility for the Project, which moreover benefits from the funnelling of users from the social network pages to its Website. Crucially, social network activity can be planned more easily than other forms of promotion thanks to the availability of relevant

metrics. Thus social networks help spread online word-of-mouth about the research progress and the wealth of Project materials made available on the Website.

Based on our target demographics, we activated SMART-electron profiles on the main social networks. We recently re-assessed SN presence and activities based on metrics as well as on a survey which was circulated amongst TEM and quantum optics scientists, which confirmed the importance of LinkedIn as a platform for reaching through to scientists. Here are the corresponding links:

Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/SMART-electron>

LinkedIn

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/smart-electron-79b358216/>

Twitter

https://twitter.com/sm_electron

Instagram

<https://www.instagram.com/smelectron/?hl=en>

Content for social networks

Social networks are an essential tool for communicating the project and building a community of interested users around it.

Highly engaging content -in the form of science news, beautiful images, pregnant quotes, scientists' selfies or short mobile video testimonials taken during their work, etc.- are being regularly posted and promoted. Relevant existing communities, groups, and pages will be exploited to this end. A-B testing of Facebook posts is employed systematically, taking advantage of the various metrics provided by the platform.

It is important to realise that SNs are media channels in their own right and, as such, need a clear editorial guideline and regular updates backed by a publishing plan drafted at regular intervals. To this end, social network posts for SMART-electron are created so as to conform to either one of the following categories:

1) General science posts

General-interest quirky science posts, pertaining mostly to the physical sciences and with particular emphasis to TEM. These can also be reposts of existing excellent articles, with which we share the same target audience.

2) SMART-electron news and EC news

These are SMART-electron news proper: papers published, prizes, events, etc. EC news on R&I are part of this category.

3) Testimonials from researchers

These are images or interviews related to SMART-electron, chronicling work through personal perspective/updates, and thus bringing out the 'human element' behind scientific research.

4) Basic science terms explained

These are short posts on basic SMART-electron science concepts, explained by specialists: didactic but easy posts on basic subjects, such as what is the superposition of states, what is a SEM, what is coherence, etc.

5) Brilliant TEM images

Large, beautiful TEM images with a short caption explaining what they depict.

The SMART-electron Twitter Page – Snapshot

- **Partners' involvement**

Partners are encouraged to promote SMART-electron activities and outcomes on their institutional mailing lists, newsletters/e-bulletins, and social media channels.

SMART-electron Partners regularly attend relevant scientific conferences, where they disseminate project brochures.

Greater Partner involvement in outreach in general has been sought by:

- establishing a common repository where partners can upload images to be used for outreach, especially for social networks
- establishing a regular conf call between all Partners devoted to discussing new outreach opportunities and ideas
- providing training to Partners for taking better pictures, so as to enable them to provide significant snapshots of various aspects of lab life.

- **Synergies with Wikimedia**

Regular Wiki Edit-a-thons are being organised with the aim of editing and improving Wikipedia entries on SMART-electron-specific topics. This approach allows SMART-electron to tap into the large user base of Wikipedia. The importance of the synergy with Wikipedia, with its >60 million daily readers², cannot be underestimated.

Selected SMART-electron images will also be published also in Wikimedia Commons thanks to the support of [Wikimedia Italia](#); this will also give Wikipedia users the possibility to directly access (and reference in articles) a plethora of significant scientific sources.

² Source: <https://analytics.wikimedia.org/dashboards/reportcard/#daily-unique-devices>

- **Synergies with EFFECT Project**

Dissemination synergies with the [EFFECT Project](#) (a.k.a. FETfx) are important for both communication and dissemination. A cooperation agreement with EFFECT is currently being pursued to this end. From a strategic point of view, dissemination of SMART-electron outcomes among experts reached through EFFECT means that sorter-related technologies developed in SMART-electron might gain further new users across Europe.

- **Synergies with other SMART-electron ‘sister’ projects +eBEAM (Pohlmann)**

SMART-electron liaises and will liaise with other sister projects to ensure full and effective collaboration within the FET programme framework and the related flagship initiatives of the European Commission, including the [Quantum Manifesto](#) and [Quantera](#).

Moreover, SMART-electron is consolidating its relationship with international projects such as [MINEON](#), [Q-SORT](#), [EBEAM](#), [QEM](#) and the [Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#).

- **Synergies with Open Access projects**

The main ongoing projects facilitating and advancing OpenAccess belong to the OpenAIRE infrastructure:

- OpenAIRE-Advance: H2020 project consolidating and operating OpenAIRE services, making them EOSC compatible.

- OpenAIRE-Connect: H2020 project outreaching its services to research communities and research infrastructures.

- OpenAIRE2020: H2020 project consolidating OA to FP7 publications, expanding to a full 100% mandate in H2020, and supporting the Open Research Data pilot of H2020.

SMART-electron is liaising with the above projects and in 2019 has hosted a special Webinar about Open Access in collaboration with OpenAIRE.

- **External events**

Other important channels for the dissemination of project results include national networks, European and International workshops, seminars, and conferences organised by other institutions, as well as national and international fairs and exhibitions.

Individual SMART-electron members regularly attend relevant conferences and sister-project events and disseminate project brochures. Project brochures are also occasionally sent for deployment to event organisers.

SMART-electron personnel also participates in relevant communication and/or networking events organised by the European Commission, such as the European Innovation Council Future Tech Week or the European Researchers' Night.

- **Scientific papers**

All partners are encouraged to author papers in international journals, as well as conference proceedings where partners are invited to present their papers. To this end, many SMART-electron deliverables have been conceived as manuscripts for research papers, so as to optimise the time and effort spent doing research. All research papers generated by SMART-electron bear the official acknowledgement of EC funding, specifying the Grant Agreement number.

- **SMART-electron publications and News**

Printed and online proceedings, in the form of a Book of Abstracts will be produced by WP6 in cooperation with UNIMIB, in order to disseminate the outcomes achieved by the various WPs to a wider public.

- **SMART-electron Events**

These are central to the dissemination and engagement. They consist of:

- a. 4 dedicated SMART-electron International Conferences, scheduled to work in synergy with major conferences held by sister projects and to dovetail with major related conferences;
- b. 3 Wikipedia Edit-a-thons
- c. related deployment of specific promotional materials:
 - i. Conference posters;
 - ii. Project brochures.

List of SMART-electron Public Events

Event	Date	Expected Audience	Location	Status
Kick-off Meeting	M1	All partners, European Commission, Civil Society Organisation (E.g. Wikimedia)	Virtual	Done
SMART-electron First International Conference	M8-M12	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Virtual	Done
SMART-electron Second International Conference	M18-M24	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community		To be organised
SMART-electron Third International Conference	M28-M36	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community		To be organised
SMART-electron Fourth International Conference	M40-M48	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community		To be organised
SMART-electron Science Bashes	M18-M24 / M28-M36 / M40-M48	General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Same ones as those of the International	To be organised

			Conferences, if possible	
SMART-electron Edit-a-Thons	M18-M24 / M28-M36 / M40-M48	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Same ones as those of the International Conferences, if possible	To be organised
Additional engagement events organised				
European Researchers' Night	September 2021	Research Community General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, (Italy) To be defined	Done
Q-SORT - SMART-electron seminar	May 2021	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	CNR-NANO (Italy)	Done

SUMMARY OF CHANNELS/ACTIONS

The following table sums up the methods employed by Q-SORT to disseminate its activities and outcomes.

METHOD	PURPOSE	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCES	GUIDELINES FOR PARTNERS
Project website	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Communicate</i>	The Project Website is one of the most versatile dissemination tools. It should 'speak' to different audiences, using the appropriate linguistic tools.	See <i>D6.1 Project logo and webpage</i> . This deliverable describes the website developed for the project, in particular the goals it intends to achieve, the users towards whom it is targeted, the software used, the structure of the public and the reserved areas, the implementation work, the services, the editorial board, the tools for monitoring the website.	Partners are encouraged to send relevant information, news, images to enrich the Project Website and be shared by all.
Partners' institutional websites	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Pages or dedicated pages on these websites are important for the dissemination of the project's results at a national level and to direct traffic towards the Project Website		Partners are encouraged to publish a page or section describing the project's activities and results on their institutional websites.

Social networks groups & Mailing- lists	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	All these tools present an opportunity to be proactive and reactive, to share one's knowledge with the target community, to develop a brand image for SMART-electron and to help spread online word-of-mouth about the progress of research.		Partners are encouraged to follow SMART-electron Social Networks profiles. Partners who manage a professional blog or who are active on social networks are encouraged to promote and disseminate the Project and its results to their own audiences. Partners are encouraged to announce their achievements, publications, etc.
Wikimedia	<i>To:</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Opening up Wikimedia to experts interested in the topics of SMART-electron.		Partners are encouraged to edit Wikipedia entries and enrich the Wikimedia Commons with images produced during the project.
Press Releases and Newsletters	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Communicate</i>	A press release is a formal announcement to the national press. Partners are encouraged to issue press releases to announce any event or important SMART-electron achievement.		Partners should liaise with the SMART-electron coordinator before issuing a press release and to include the SMART-electron logo, e-mail and link to the website.
Brochures and other promotional material	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>communicate</i>	Though communication channels are often electronic, we believe that it is still useful to circulate printed dissemination materials at meetings and events.	The following materials will be available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMART-electron brochure • SMART-electron Poster Dissemination material may be downloaded from a dedicated page in the Project Website. A detailed description of SMART-electron Dissemination material will be provided in the related deliverable D6.5. This document will be structured as an easy-to-use internal guide describing dissemination materials that have been	Partners should disseminate SMART-electron promotional material at their professional events. All promotional material will be available for customisation and translation into other languages.

			completed or will be available in the near future, as well as guidelines on how, where and when to distribute them.	
Sister projects and cluster meetings organised by the European Commission	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>communicate</i>	Sister projects and cluster meetings are excellent opportunities for projects to learn from each other, discuss common issues, and receive feedback on their work. Partners may be asked to give a presentation, participate in a workshop, give a demo, etc. As there may be many projects on the agenda, we encourage partners to make an impact and engage the audience.	Events archive on SMART-electron website Messages circulating in professional mailing list	Partners are advised to use the Project Website and internal mailing lists to inform all partners about professional meetings. Some of SMART-electron's experts could be interested in participating in one of them. Partners are required to always include the corporate image when presenting or speaking about SMART-electron.
Conference presentations	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>communicate</i>	National and international conferences are an excellent opportunity to share the network's achievements with experts in the field (teaching/ learning, etc).	Events archive on SMART-electron website	Partners are advised to make sure they select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts they want to speak to. Partners are directed to always use the corporate image when presenting or speaking about SMART-electron. Partners are encouraged to distribute SMART-electron promotional material.
Conference posters	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i>	A poster session at a conference may be more appropriate when there is work in progress. Posters may be presented to delegates who attend the session. It may not be as engaging as doing a presentation in the auditorium, but it's an excellent		Partners are advised to make sure they select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts they want to speak to. Partners are advised to always include the SMART-electron corporate image.

		<p>way to attract people and get one-on-one feedback. Often conferences do not foresee calls for papers, but do foresee poster sessions.</p>		<p>Partners are encouraged to distribute SMART-electron promotional material.</p>
<p>SMART-electron Science Bashes</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>Science Bashes are events that take place in casual settings such as pubs and coffeehouses. They are open to everyone, and feature an engaging conversation with a scientist about a particular topic. Science Bashes represent a grassroots movement. They exist all over the world and can vary from place to place. Venues range from local libraries, to school and coffee houses to neighborhood bars. Even the names of Science Bashes vary, including Science on Tap, Science Pub, Ask a Scientist, and Café Sci.</p>		<p>Partners should provide topics for the Science Bashes and engage the local communities in these events.</p> <p>Partners will be advised to distribute SMART-electron promotional material on these occasions.</p>
<p>Wikipedia Edit-a-thons</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>An edit-a-thon is</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a scheduled time where people edit Wikipedia together, whether offline, online, or a mix of both; 2. typically focused on a specific topic, such as science or women's history. 3. a way to recruit new Wikipedians and teach them how to contribute. Edit-a-thons improve the encyclopedia and 		<p>Partners should provide topics for the edit-a-thons, engage the local communities in these events and to get in touch with the respective national chapter of Wikimedia.</p>

		<p>can be a great way to help new Wikipedians learn to edit. This is quite different from large conferences such as Wikimania, which often have multiple speakers or panels about a huge variety of topics. An edit-a-thon is also unlike a regular meetup, which tends to be without a single goal and/or for socializing. In other words, an edit-a-thon is like a hackathon for Wikipedians.</p>		
<p>Journal articles and/or Publications</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i></p>	<p>Partners are encouraged at every opportunity to author articles on the SMART-electron project.</p> <p>During the project, partners may wish to contribute to electronic newsletters, blogs, portals.</p> <p>Peer reviewed journals in relevant disciplines will be a very important opportunity once we will have reached an advanced phase of the project, when there are data and results to report.</p>		<p>Partners are advised to include in their work references to the SMART-electron project.</p> <p>Partners must inform and send a copy of any journal article or academic paper to the project's coordinator so that it may be published or mentioned on the SMART-electron website.</p>
<p>ZENODO</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Share data</i></p>	<p>Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit data sets,</p>		<p>Partners must inform and send a copy of any journal article or academic paper or deliverable to the project's coordinator so that it may be uploaded to the ZENODO repository.</p>

		<p>research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts. SMART-electron opened its own <i>community</i> on Zenodo on which it collects the most relevant project data.</p>		
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5 MONITORING AND SUCCESS INDICATORS

The following table lists the updated **success indicators** regarding the Project's dissemination, communication, and public engagement efforts.

Indicator No.	Objective/expected result	Indicator name	Expected Progress		
			M12	M30	M48
1	Communication and engagement success	Total number of followers on social networks	500	1000	1500
2	Communication and engagement success	Maximum post reach on social networks	1000	2000	5000
3	Communication success	Number of countries reached through social networks and website	8	16	28
4	Communication and dissemination success	Number of visitors on Project Website (unique IPs)	150	500	750
5	Communication and dissemination success	Total number of brochures/flyers distributed	1000	4000	7000
6	Dissemination success	Number of conferences attended by SMART-electron scientists	12	30	42
7	Dissemination success	Number of papers published	3	5	11
8	Dissemination success	Number of Project Events organised by SMART-electron	1	2	4
9	Dissemination success	Number of participants in the events organised by the SMART-electron	60	120	200
10	Communication and dissemination success	Number of visits to the SMART-electron Website	500	2000	5000
11	Dissemination success	Number of citations of SMART-electron papers	4	14	28
12	Engagement and communication success	Number of quotations or links or embeds of the SMART-electron	30	100	200

		project (Web, including social networks)			
13	Engagement success	Number of Wiki Edit-a-thons	1	2	3
14	Engagement success	Number of Science Bashes	1	2	3
15	Engagement success	Number of 'share' actions on Social Networks	100	200	300
16	Engagement success	Number of items (articles or media) enriched in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons	10	20	30

The effectiveness of dissemination and engagement activities is evaluated constantly with the following criteria:

1) Statistical analysis of the Project Website with the following indicators, in order to follow up on users' interest through Website content:

- Page views: number of webpages requested and viewed by the user;
- Visits or sessions: number of visits to the site made by users;
- Unique visitors: number of single users that have visited the site;
- Time spent: time spent in minutes and seconds while navigating or viewing the pages of a site or using a digital application.

[Google Analytics](#) is the main tool to collect fresh insights into how visitors use our site, how they arrived at our site, which parts of our website are performing well, which pages are most popular and how visitors interact with sharing features on the site.

In addition, the SMART-electron social network profiles are managed through [Hootsuite](#), a social media management tool that allows the SMART-electron dissemination team to efficiently track conversations and measure our dissemination campaign results.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to ensure that:

- the Project overall outreach activities follow the planned schedule and meet with success;
- the messages delivered from the Project to the 'outer world' are coherent and of a high standard;
- the Project maintains a high profile;
- the Project community at large learns from its achievements.

The Project Coordinator, together with partner QED, will share the strategy developed in this document with all the partners and the WP Leaders, inviting them to contribute ideas for the duration of the project.

Envisioning an overall outreach plan at the beginning of the project ensures that we maximise the impact of dissemination, communication, and public engagement.

In order to make the Dissemination and Communication Plan effective, we have broken it down into a clear and specific set of constituent elements:

Goals: We set out at the beginning the objectives of our dissemination and communication efforts.

Target Audience and Message: We have identified and described the main target audiences of SMART-electron. For each of the target audiences, we have established the basic elements of the message to be disseminated.

Methods: We have described the media channels and the strategies through which the message of SMART-electron can be best delivered and established a set of clear and simple branding guidelines.

Success: We have listed the metrics to measure success and monitor progress.

ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO-BICOCCA	ITALY	UNIMIB
2 ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE EPFL	SWITZERLAND	EPFL
3 FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE CIENCIES FOTONIQUES	SPAIN	ICFO
4 TECHNION - ISRAEL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	ISRAEL	TECHNION
5 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
6 HOLOEYE PHOTONICS AG	GERMANY	HOLOEYE
7 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UK	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL